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Progress of SOC development at Elcogen

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Abstract

Elcogen is one of the leading European manufacturers of solid oxide cell (SOC) technology. Elcogen products are unique combination of best in class performance and low-cost product structure. The unit cell and stack products are designed for low temperature operation enabling major cost reductions in the system level. Elcogen's operations are located in the Nordic-Baltic technology cluster of Finland and Estonia. This article summarizes the recent activities and development trends of Elcogen.

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Introduction

Elcogen is currently focused in ramping up its unit cell and stack production with the increased customer requests. The short-term goal is to set-up of a demonstration manufacturing plant for the unit cells and stacks with annual capacity of 50 MW. To facilitate the goals, Elcogen has signed EUR 12 million loan facility with The European Investment Bank (EIB). The loan is the first in the Baltic countries to get support under the InnovFin – EU-finance for innovators programme, which is financed from the EU's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme. Specifically, the financing falls under InnovFin's Energy Demonstration Projects (EDP) facility.

Elcogen is continuously developing its products for higher performance, longer lifetime, lower costs, increased quality and expanded applications. This article summarizes Elcogen's latest test results of its commercial E3000 stack conducted to study the performance, long-term stability, thermocycle durability and manufacturing quality.

Elcogen stacks are built around company's internally manufactured unit cells. The unit cells are anode supported with cell structure combining anode contact layer (NiO, 2 μm), anode support layer (NiO/YSZ, 400 μm), anode functional layer (NiO/YSZ, 10 μm), electrolyte (YSZ, 3 μm), barrier layer (GDC, 2 μm), and cathode (LSC, 20 μm). The interconnect plates are manufactured from ferritic sheet metal and coated with MCO. The stack design for commercial application is called elcoStack[®] E3000 and the stack design for technology evaluation purposes elcoStack[®] E350. The difference between the design variants is the air supply means, i.e. elcoStack[®] E350 has fully manifolded air side structure as elcoStack[®] E3000 utilizes open air design. Figure 1 depicts elcoStack[®] E350 and elcoStack[®] E3000. The flow distribution and electrical contacting structures for both design variants are identical and thus the results obtained with both designs are directly comparable to each other. elcoStack[®] E350 design is easily integrable to most solid oxide fuel cell test stands and elcoStack[®] E3000 is optimized for large systems utilizing multiple stacks.

Figure 1. a) elcoStack[®] E350 with 15 unit layers, fully manifolded air structure, all unit layers equipped with voltage measurement cables and in-stack thermocouple. b) elcoStack[®] E3000 with 119 unit layers and open air structure.

1. Performance and manufacturing quality

The main stack product for Elcogen is elcoStack[®] E3000. This is optimized for large SOFC systems utilizing multiple stacks. An example of such system is developed in EU's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No 671403. Elcogen manufactures stacks to the system and Convion Ltd. is responsible for the system design and manufacturing.

In order to enable successful fuel cell systems, the stack quality has to be constant. Thus, Elcogen is monitoring the performance of every produced stack with quality assurance tests with as high detail level as is still practical without increasing the manufacturing costs. Elcogen's standard quality assurance protocol includes current-voltage characteristics test and effective fuel utilization dependency test. Quality assurance measurements are conducted according to IEC 62282-7-2. Stack temperature is recorded with two thermocouples, the first located at the inlet edge of the active cell area and the second one located at the outlet edge of the active cell area.

The current-voltage characteristics test is conducted with 1/1 ratio of H₂/N₂ with constant flow rate of 122 lN/min. Cathode side is fed with air at constant flow rate of 327 lN/min. Inlet temperature for the air is 590 °C and for the fuel 585 °C. Current is increased with 1 A/min sweep rate from 0A to 30A. The stack power is calculated as a product of the measured current and voltage.

The effective fuel utilization dependency test is conducted at constant current of 20 A. The test is conducted at partial load in order to highlight possible differences in the fuel utilization dependency between the stacks. Fuel is 1/1 ratio of H₂/N₂, and the fuel flow rate is decreased stepwise 54.6 – 50.3 – 46.7 – 45.0 – 43.7 – 42.3 – 40.8 lN/min. Stabilization time at each flow rate level is 2 min. Cathode side is fed with air at constant flow rate of 327 lN/min. Inlet temperature for the air is 590 °C and for the fuel 585 °C.

The current-voltage characteristics test results are depicted in Fig. 2. The average stack voltage at open circuit condition of elcoStack[®] E3000 is 141.8 V with standard deviation of 0.8 V. The mean unit layer voltage is 1.191 V and the deviation per unit layer is 0.007 V. The average stack voltage at nominal current, 30A, of elcoStack[®] E3000 is 105.0 V with standard deviation of 0.6 V. The mean unit layer voltage is 0.883 V and the deviation per unit layer is 0.005 V. The average stack temperature determined as the average between the stack inlet temperature (605 °C) and stack outlet temperature (667 °C) at the nominal current is measured to be 636 °C. Stack power at 30A is 3151 W with standard deviation of 23 W. The deviation per unit layer is 0.2 W as a single layer produces 26.5 W.

The effective fuel utilization dependency test results are depicted in Fig. 3. The average stack voltage of elcoStack[®] E3000 at 60% fuel utilization is 108.2 V with standard deviation of 0.3 V. The average stack voltage of elcoStack[®] E3000 at 80% fuel utilization is 104.5 V with standard deviation of 0.3 V. The deviation per unit layer is constant 0.003 V at these fuel utilization levels.

Figure 2. Current-voltage characteristics of elcoStack[®] E3000 measured with hydrogen. Error bars are calculated as standard deviations of the measured stacks.

Figure 3. Effective fuel utilization dependency of elcoStack[®] E3000. Error bars are calculated as standard deviations of the measured stacks.

The current-voltage characteristics test with natural gas is conducted with 1/2.2 ratio of NG/H₂O with constant flow rate of 33 l_N/min. The gas composition is typical Finnish pipeline grade natural gas with lower heating value of 802.3 kJ/mol ([CH₄] = 98%, [C₂H₆] = 0.8%, [C₃H₈] = 0.2 %, [C₄H₁₀] = 0.02%, [N₂] = 0.9 %, [CO₂] = 0.1%). The odorant in natural gas, THT, is cleaned with a room temperature sorbent. Test is conducted at VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd. Natural gas is mixed with steam feed prior the reformer reactor. The gas composition fed to the stack is standardized in the test by controlling the outlet temperature of the steam reforming reactor to 590 °C. The resulting composition for the stack inlet is [CH₄] = 7%, [H₂O] = 26%, [CO] = 7%, [H₂] = 52%, [CO₂] = 8%. Cathode side is fed with air at constant flow rate of 327 l_N/min. Inlet temperature for the air and fuel is 590 °C. Current is increased with 1A/min sweep rate from 0A to 30A. The stack power is calculated as a product of the measured current and voltage.

Figure 3. elcoStack[®] E3000 performance measured with natural gas.

2. Long-Term Stability

The long-term stability of elcoStack[®] is studied with steam reformed natural gas. The long-term stability experiment is conducted with standard elcoStack[®] material system and with two type stack configurations, E3000 and E350, see Fig. 1. Difference between the two stacks is the number of unit layers and the air side flow configuration. – E350 contains 15 and E3000 119 unit layers. E350 has closed air manifold structure and E3000 has an open-air structure as shown in Fig. 1.

Both stack tests are conducted at VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd. Testing conditions for the stacks are set to equal in terms of temperatures, current, fuel composition and flow rates per unit layers. Natural gas is mixed with steam feed prior the reformer reactor. The steam-to-natural gas ratio is 2.2. The gas composition fed to the stack is standardized in the test by controlling the outlet temperature of the steam reforming reactor to 590 °C. The resulting composition for the stack inlet is [CH₄] = 7%, [H₂O] = 26%, [CO] = 7%, [H₂] = 52%, [CO₂] = 8%. Fuel utilization in the test is 60% simulating conditions of a system equipped with anode exhaust gas recycle unit. The fuel cell cathode is fed with preheated air. The oxygen utilization is 22%. Both the air and fuel are heated to 590 °C for the stack inlet. The current at the nominal operation conditions is 30 A.

Figure 4 depicts the average unit layer voltage as a function of operation time for E3000 stack and the average unit layer voltage for unit layers 8 – 11 as a function of operation time for E350 stack. Layers 8 – 11 from E350 test are selected for this analysis due to their similar temperature profile nature compared to E3000 stack, i.e. end cell effects are then excluded from the analysis. The E350 has been operated at constant steam reforming conditions for 18700 hours and the test is still continued (August, 2020). The voltage decay over the whole operation time has been 0.4 %/1000h and the ASR decay 15 mΩ.cm²/1000h. The voltage decay is determined as the slope divided by the intercept of linear regression of the mean unit layer voltage measured at the nominal conditions. The ASR decay is determined as the slope of linear regression of the mean unit layer voltage

measured at the nominal conditions divided by the current density ($0.25 \text{ A}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$). The test period involves one load cycle at 5600 hours in which the current was switch off from 30 A to 0A instantly and full thermocycles due to scheduled laboratory maintenance at 7600 and 8600 hours. None of these interruptions caused any measurable degradation to the stack voltage. elcoStack[®] E3000 has been operated since June 2020 with natural gas achieving 1400 loading hours. The initial performance and degradation levels are comparable to the E350 test as can be seen from Fig 4 and the test is continued.

Figure 4. elcoStack[®] average voltage in long-term test.

3. Robustness in thermocycles

elcoStack[®] E3000 robustness in thermocycles is studied with conventional heat cycle process in which reducing gas is continuously supplied to the anode side and air to the cathode side, see Fig. 5. One cycle consists of a heating period from 50 °C to 600 °C at rate of 120 °C/h, testing period and a cooling period from 600 °C to 50 °C. During heating and testing periods, fuel side is fed with 1/1 mixture of H_2/N_2 at 122 l_N/min flow rate expect effective fuel utilization test in which ratio is kept constant but flow rate is decreased. During cooling phase, fuel side is fed with 5/95 mixture of H_2/N_2 at 106 l_N/min flow rate. Air side is fed with constant flow rate of 327 l_N/min. Testing phase includes current-voltage characteristics test and effective fuel utilization test, and these both are conducted with a similar process already explained previously. Stack is equipped with unit layer voltage measurement cables.

Figure 5. Temperature and gas flow rates in thermocycling testing.

Thermocycling test is conducted all together 11 times for the stack. Figure 6 depicts the stack voltage (diamonds) during the current-voltage characterization test at 0 A (OCV) and 30 A (NOC). The area around the diamonds indicate the difference between the maximum unit layer voltage and the minimum unit layer voltage. It is observed that no decay in stack voltage could be observed during the cycling test but actually the performance of the stack was improving. E.g. stack voltage after stack conditioning process was 138.8 V at OCV and 105.7 V at NOC, after 5 cycles was 141.6 V (OCV) and 107.0 V (NOC) and after 10 cycles 142.0 V (OCV) and 107.5 V (NOC). At respective cycles, the difference between the maximum and minimum unit layer voltages was 26 mV (OCV, cycle 0), 35 mV (OCV, cycle 5), 35 (OCV, cycle 10), and 47 mV (NOC, cycle 0), 50 mV (NOC, cycle 5), 47 mV (NOC, cycle 10).

Figure 6. elcoStack® E3000 voltage in thermocycles. A diamond is stack voltage and average unit layer voltage, area is defined as the difference between the maximum and minimum unit layer voltage. Blue color indicates OCV values and green color NOC values.

4. Summary

Elcogen is continuously developing its unit cell and stack products to be more efficient, robust and affordable for different applications. Elcogen products are unique as their operation temperature is 600 °C still being able of utilizing standard industrial materials and manufacturing methods allowing major cost reductions for the technology. This work summarizes some of the latest test results of Elcogen stack products highlighting the robustness, constant quality and long-term stability of elcoStack[®] E3000 products.

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